

BLOOD PATHOLOGY OF RABBITS IN PASTEURELLOSIS

Nabieva Naima Akhmedovna

Veterinary Science Research independent researcher

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Abstract. *In the Microbiology Laboratory of the Veterinary Research Institute, an experiment was carried out on eight rabbits. In this case, rabbits were allocated to four main experimental groups and four main control groups. Rabbits in the experimental group were infected with an abdominal cavity of 0.5 ml at a rate of LD50 1 mlyar from the causative agent, Pasteurella multocida, and blood was drawn from the supraocular region and analyzed beginning on the first day of the experiment. Blood leukoformula was used to detect rabbits.*

Keywords: *Pasteurella multocida, rabbit, lecoformula, lecoocyte, gronulacitis, monocyte, blood, pathology, blood enema, phogocytosis.*

Introduction: In Pasteurella multocida in Pasteurella pasteurellosis of rabbits, breathing increases in the organs, then enters the blood and lymph and spreads throughout the body in the enema and tissues. This also causes drastic changes in rabbits' blood markers. Pasteurella multocida secretes factors that inhibit phagocytosis, reducing the phagocytic properties of blood cells, resulting in an unhindered increase in sepsis, the name of the condition. As a result of the destruction of Pasteurella in the body, endotoxin is released, which affects the vascular walls, migrates the accumulation of diapedesis, inflammatory edema, and serous-hemorrhagic exudate, and calls for dystrophic processes in parenchymal organs. In the nervous system, the activity of immunopoesis in the organs slows down. In particular, scientists have shown that rabbits are affected by the normal physiological state of the blood due to the fact that pathological processes in the organs are observed by infecting Pasteurella multocida, in which, when hematologically carried out examinations are carried out, a very significant change in the blood of a rabbit with pasteurellosis is observed, with an increase in the number of red blood cells. Compared to controlled rabbits, it was found that the number of white blood cells increased, while lymphocytes had an increased content of monocytes and neutrophils. [Ульхина Л.И. 2004, Ятусевич А.И. и других 2008, El-Hendy H.M. A. 2020, et al. 2020, El-Hendy H.M. A. 2020].

Purpose of the study: in the course of our research, rabbits in the experimental group infected with Pasteurella multocida in laboratory conditions were determined which pointers changed in comparison with the determination of changes in blood markers and comparing the lecoformule in the blood of Health rabbits in the control group. Materials and methods of research: veterinary scientific research Institut's Microbiology Laboratory conducted an experiment on 8 head rabbits. In this case, rabbits were allocated to 4 main experimental groups and 4 main control groups. The rabbits in the experimental group were infected with the abdominal cavity in ld 50 1 mlyar from the pathogen Pasteurella multocida, and from the first day of the experiment, blood was taken from the ear spray and analyzed, in which a lecoformule of blood was detected. In this case, Mindraz BS 30 s was detected in hematologichisky Aparat. To do this, 2 ml of blood was taken and placed in a test tube on the aparat bench result, released in 10 seconds to the monitor.

Results of the study: according to the result of the study, 8 Heads of rabbits were separated into 1 experimental group and 2 control groups, and rabbits in the Experimental Group (4 heads)

were infested with *Pasteurella multocida*. Rabbits in the control group (4 heads) were not affected, and the result of blood sampling from them was checked (in 1 table).

Lekositar formula of blood in rabbits pasterellosis

1-Table

In this table, it was found that in the experimental group, when the leucocyte content of

Number of rabbits in groups	The amount of leukocytes is 10/9 liters Lymph#	The number of lymphocytes is 10/9 liters Mid#	The number of monocytes is 10/9 liters	The amount of granulocytes is 10/9 liters	Lymphocyte Amount Lymph%	Monocyte count Mid%	The amount of granulocytes Gran%	Hematocrit HC T%	Average volume of erythrocytes MCV f/l
Rabbits in the 1-group experimental	12,2	4,6	2,5	9,6	33,2	12,5	56,8	20,7	58,2
Rabbits in control group-2	8,5	2,94	1,10	7,23	29,8	9,3	49	39,1	77,5

rabbits was taken to the feziological norm, 3,710/9 liters of lymph were raised due to the presence of an exudative process in the rabbit's organism, and the amount of leucocyte in the lungs was increased due to the occurrence of necrotic processes in the rabbit's organism. There was a decrease in the indication of hematocrit and lymphocyte content in the blood due to the decrease in erythrocytes; the amount of monocyte granulocyte increased compared to the increased feziological norm; a significant result was observed in the remaining blood markers with a decrease in the average concentration of hemoglobin erythrocyte that did not return. In this case, it was found that in the blood of rabbits used in the experiment, the markers of leucocytes and their composition in the immune system were elevated in lymphocytes, monocytes, and granulocytes.

Discussion of the topic: rabbits cause pathological processes in the spleen, thymus, red marrow, and lymph nodes in the organs where blood cells are formed in pasterellosis, as a result of which damage to the immune system occurs in the blood markers. Confirming the same data, this experiment also observed an increase in the amount of leucocyte, which is the basis of the immune system, and a decrease in monocytes.

Conclusion: In the course of research, it was found that in rabbits infected with *Pasteurella*, the amount of leukocytes increased by a ratio of 3,710/9 liters compared to the norm.

2. The hematocrit of the spectator was found to be 18.4% lower than the feziological norm.
3. Lymphocytes were found to increase by 3.4%.
4. It was found that monosodium increased by 3.2%.

5. It was found that hemoglobin rose by 27.3% compared to the norm in the average concentration of erythrocytes. From this general conclusion in rabbit pasteurellosis, this demonstrative change was observed as a result of serious damage to the body's immune system in the event of a pathological process in parenchymal organs.

REFERENCES

1. Ятусевич А.И. Прудников В.С, Карасев Н.Ф, Николевнко М.Ф «Зараные болезни пушних зверей» Монография Витебск-2008. с-10-12.
2. Улыхина Л.И. «Спаровочник кролиководство» / Ростов-на-Дону Фенкс 2004 г. с-216-218.
3. Арипов А.И, Фесенко Л.М,Арипов О.А, Исмоилов Н.И,Мухамедияров Р.Г, Клиник лаборатор диагностика бўйича қўлланма Тошкент-2007 йил б-12-56.
4. El-Hendi H. M. A, Mahamed F. M., Hassan K. A // Clinopathological and hematological changes as a result of Type A experimental infection in *Pasteurella multocida* of rabbits // SVU-International Journal of Veterinary Science 3 (2): Egypt 2020, P-1-13.